

MISTAKES IN ACADEMIC WRITING AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

Raxmanova Dildora Abdulxamid qizi

Namangan State University, Faculty of World languages, English Language and Literature
department

Gmail: raxdildora18@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10815512>

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim talabalari tomonidan ingliz tilida ilmiy yozuvda yozish jarayonida qilinadigan xatolar va ularning yechimlari xususida so'z boradi. Maqolada talabalar bilan o'tkazilgan so'rovnomma va uning natijalari muhokama qilinadi, tavsiyalar beriladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Akademik yozuv muammolari, ilmiy yozuv, tanqidiy fikrlash, ilmiy yondashuv, iqtibos keltirish*

Аннотация. *В этой статье рассматриваются причины ошибок академического письма на английском языке, допущенные студентами университетов, и предпринимается попытка предложить некоторые действенные решения. Будет представлена анкета и обсуждены ее результаты.*

Ключевые слова : *Проблемы академического письма, научное письмо, критическое мышление, научный подход, цитирование.*

Abstract. *This article examines the causes of academic writing errors in English made by university students and attempts to offer some workable solutions. Questionnaire will be presented and its results are discussed.*

Keywords : *Academic writing problems, scientific writing, critical thinking, scientific approach, citation*

Introduction

Students make numerous mistakes when it comes to producing English academic writing. These errors include difficulty in distinguishing between spoken and written English, struggling to make an outline before drafting, identifying the necessary skills for successful writing, and avoiding commonly used phrases and words that can lead to plagiarism. Additionally, many Uzbek students lack the necessary guidance and feedback from their lecturers during the academic writing process, hindering their development in this area. Furthermore, non-native English-speaking students from Uzbekistan who are planning to study in British or other Western universities may encounter additional challenges with academic writing. The challenges faced by Uzbek students in academic writing are varied and complex. Despite the difficulties in distinguishing between spoken and written English and the lack of guidance from lecturers, it is important for students to seek out resources and support to improve their academic writing skills. With determination and practice, Uzbek students can overcome these challenges and excel in their academic pursuits. Additionally, institutions and educators should provide more targeted support and resources to help Uzbek students navigate the nuances of English academic writing. By addressing these challenges, Uzbek students can enhance their academic writing abilities and succeed in their educational endeavors.

Effective academic writing is essential for conveying our ideas clearly and persuasively. However, many students and scholars struggle with common mistakes that can detract from the quality of their work. (Fatimah, 2019) By understanding the reasons behind these academic writing mistakes, you can take proactive steps to improve the clarity and impact of your writing. In this

paper, we will explore some of the key reasons behind common academic writing mistakes and provide strategies for overcoming them. The main reasons for academic writing mistakes in English can be attributed to lack of attention to grammatical and spelling errors, inadequate understanding of proper structure and organization of the text, limited familiarity with academic writing conventions and norms, and difficulties in integrating and synthesizing information from different sources (Ramoroka.B.T, 2014) .These factors contribute to errors in grammar, punctuation, and spelling, as well as problems with coherence, cohesion, and logical flow in the writing. Additionally, the pressure to meet deadlines and the temptation to engage in plagiarism or improper citation practices can also contribute to academic writing mistakes. Furthermore, the lack of sufficient practice and feedback in academic writing can hinder the development of effective writing skills (Sothorn,Walwork, 2020)

These mistakes can undermine the credibility and impact of your work, making it harder for readers to understand and engage with your ideas. Therefore, addressing these reasons for academic writing mistakes is crucial for becoming a proficient and effective academic writer.

Literature review

It is undeniable that academic writing mistakes can detract from the overall quality and impact of a piece of work. However, it is important to recognize that while adherence to grammatical and spelling rules is important, overly strict adherence to these rules can stifle creativity and expression (Ramoroka.B.T, 2014).Academic writing conventions and norms may also restrict the diversity of perspectives and voices that can contribute to a scholarly discussion. Furthermore, the pressure to meet deadlines and the fear of plagiarism can lead to a focus on quantity over quality, resulting in rushed and superficial analysis. In a fast-paced academic environment, the focus on flawless writing may overshadow the development of critical thinking and original ideas. In addition, language barriers can also contribute to academic writing mistakes for non-native English speakers (Dema, 2020). They may struggle with vocabulary, sentence structure, and idiomatic expressions, leading to errors in their writing . Overall, there are various reasons for academic writing mistakes in English, including a lack of attention to grammar and spelling errors, challenges with proper structure and organization and the temptation to engage in plagiarism or improper citation practices. However, it is important to approach academic writing with a balanced perspective. While it is crucial to address these reasons for academic writing mistakes, it is also essential to recognize that academic writing is a skill that can be developed and improved over time. By seeking feedback, practicing regularly, and familiarizing oneself with the conventions of academic writing, one can overcome these challenges and become a proficient academic writer (Dema, 2020)

Understanding the reasons behind academic writing mistakes is the first step towards improving the quality and impact of your work. By addressing issues such as grammar and spelling errors, structure and organization, citation practices, and language barriers, you can elevate the clarity and effectiveness of your writing. Developing a balanced approach that values both precision and creativity is crucial in navigating the demands of academic writing. With dedication and practice, you can hone your academic writing skills and produce work that is both compelling and academically rigorous.

Methodology

At the end of the semester, English major students had to write and submit their course works in English from the course “Teaching language methodology” . In the second step of the

research, 30 research papers of undergraduate students were analyzed and the writing challenges clarified. Table 2 shows the mistakes done by students when they were writing their course works.

Table-2

Mistakes done by students	Number of research papers	Percent	Total
1.Academically Wrong-structured paper	11	36%	30
2.Full of grammatical errors	19	64%	30
3.Avoiding formal language	10	35%	30
4.Academically Wrong word choice	12	40%	30
5.Not including sources-citations	25	83%	30
6.Organizing paragraphs	7	23%	30

As we have seen in the survey results, students make a number of mistakes while writing in English. If we analyze their errors, 64% of the students make grammar mistakes in their papers, it shows that most of the students still struggle with lack of grammar knowledge. Majority of students were not able to write appropriate words, they have lexical errors in their writing. Almost all students did not cite their using sources in their research which is one of the biggest problems. This problem mentioned a lot in research papers :The most popular problem seen in majority of students’ work in various universities around the globe is the plagiarism that include paraphrasing without citing the sources, patch-writing, writing direct quotes without quotation marks (Zafarghandi, A. M., Khoshroo, F. & Barkat, B., 2012)

Discussion

The notion that the primary solutions to overcoming academic writing mistakes lie in increased practice and familiarity with academic norms may not address deeper educational or systemic issues. For some students, particularly those from non-traditional educational backgrounds or those with learning differences, challenges with academic writing might stem from gaps in foundational education or a lack of accessible learning resources and support, rather than simply from insufficient practice or feedback (Raxmanova, 2023)

Furthermore, while the paper suggests that addressing academic writing mistakes is crucial for becoming a proficient and effective academic writer, it's worth considering that perfection in writing should not be the sole criterion for assessing academic merit. The value of academic work also lies in the novelty and significance of the ideas presented, the depth of analysis, and the contribution to ongoing scholarly conversations. As such, a more comprehensive approach to improving academic writing might include fostering environments that encourage risk-taking, creativity, and critical thinking alongside the development of writing proficiency.

Conclusion

In summary, the initial step towards enhancing the caliber and influence of your writing is to comprehend the causes of errors in academic writing. We may improve the readability and impact of our students’ writings by addressing problems with grammar and spelling, organization and structure, citation conventions, and language hurdles. Navigating the challenges of academic writing requires developing a balanced approach that values originality and accuracy equally. We may polish learners’ academic writing abilities and generate material that is both scholarly and engaging with commitment and practice.

REFERENCES

1. Dema, K. (2020). Problems in students Academic writing. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 34-41.
2. Fatimah, N. (2019). Students’ Needs for Academic Writing at the English Education Department. *English Language Teaching*.
3. Ramoroka.B.T. (2014). Integration of sources in academic writing. *AOSIS*, 223-256.
4. Raxmanova, D. (2023). The role of writing skill in foreign language fluency. *MIASTO PRZYSZŁOŚĆ*, 382-384.
5. Sothern,Walwork. (2020). *Tips to Avoid Mistakes in Academic Writing and Presenting Southern*,. UK.
6. Zafarghandi, A. M., Khoshroo, F. & Barkat, B. (2012). “An Investigation of Iranian EFL Masters Students’ Perceptions of Plagiarism”,. ”, *International Journal for Educational Integrity* 8(2).